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Team Science Related Books and Reports: A Reading List

By Kayleigh Ward, ESIIL | May 6th, 2026

The ESIIL Team Science team has curated some books and reports useful for graduate students, postdoctoral associates and others curious about team science. This is not an exhaustive or comprehensive list, but we have attempted to keep the recommended books below as close to team science as possible given the expansive breadth of the field. The books and reports here focus on team processes most central to scientific collaboration, such as interdisciplinary integration, leadership, psychological safety, team cognition, multiteam coordination, or collaboration (in general). As a result, these books and reports are also related to organizational psychology, team cognition, management, communication, and group dynamics. For each of these we have provided a little snippet on what it covers. These are organized with the title listed first. Happy reading!

SciTS, interdisciplinary research and collaboration

Collaboration and team science: A field guide. Bennett, L. M., Gadlin, H., & Marchand, C. (2018). National Institutes of Health.

- ➔ Practical NIH-based guide for scientists, trainees, and research leaders translating collaboration research into routines for trust, communication, conflict management, mentoring, and recognition.

Strategies for team science success: Handbook of evidence-based principles for cross-disciplinary science and practical lessons learned from health researchers. Hall, K. L., Vogel, A. L., & Croyle, R. T. (Eds.). (2019). Springer.

- ➔ Comprehensive edited handbook for evidence-based principles, tools, and case-based lessons for planning, supporting, and evaluating cross-disciplinary team science.

Enhancing the effectiveness of team science. National Research Council. (2015). National Academies Press.

- ➔ Consensus report for analyzing team processes, leadership, collaboration, organizational support, and evaluation in science teams.

The science and practice of team science. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2025). National Academies Press.

- ➔ Updated National Academies roadmap for researchers covering contemporary science teams, collaboration, project management, psychological safety, accessibility, and translation.

How to Succeed at Collaborative Research: A Practical Guide for Teams. L. Michelle Bennett, M., Gadlin, H., & and Khuri, S (Eds.) (2025). Bristol University Press

- ➔ A great guide for researchers of all levels on how to lead high-performing collaborative teams with insights from team science and psychology.

Island time: Theory groups and the social production of scientific knowledge. Parker, J. (2026). Cambridge University Press.

- ➔ An in-depth ethnographic study of a theory group over 15 years. It provides practical and tacit insights into the conditions that support scientific creativity and the social dynamics of intellectual movements.

The Strength in Numbers: The New Science of Team Science. Bozeman, B., & Youtie, J. (2017). Princeton University Press.

- ➔ A great team science investigation and reflection on collaboration in STEM disciplines. It focuses on presenting a key framework on how to foster collaboration, but especially on collaboration management and effectiveness.

Interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, and boundary work

Facilitating interdisciplinary research. National Academy of Sciences, National Academy of Engineering and Medicine. (2005). National Academies Press.

- ➔ Foundational policy report on the barriers, incentives, structures, and cultures needed to support interdisciplinary collaboration.

The Oxford handbook of interdisciplinarity. Frodeman, R., Klein, J. T., & Pacheco, R. C. S. (Eds.). (2017). Oxford University Press.

- ➔ A great overview of interdisciplinary research and design, with applications for research, education, administration, and the public-sector.

Interdisciplinary research: Process and theory. Repko, A. F., & Szostak, R. (2025). SAGE.

- ➔ Great for graduate students and postdoctoral associates just becoming familiar and integrated with interdisciplinary teams and research, and who want guidance on how to define problems, integrate disciplinary insights, and build common ground in interdisciplinary teams.

Handbook of transdisciplinary research. Hirsch Hadorn, G., Hoffmann-Riem, H., Biber-Klemm, S., Grossenbacher-Mansuy, W., Joye, D., Pohl, C., Wiesmann, U., & Zemp, E. (Eds.). (2008). Springer

- ➔ A comprehensive handbook for scholars and practitioners tackling societal problems through research that integrates multiple disciplines with stakeholders beyond academia.

Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado **Boulder**

Beyond interdisciplinarity: Boundary work, communication, and collaboration. Klein, J. T. (2021). Oxford University Press.

- ➔ This provides a nice framework for expanding beyond interdisciplinarity and echoes more recent calls for boundary spanning skilling in the sciences in general. If you are new to boundary spanning and boundary work, this is for more advanced researchers and practitioners examining how boundary work, communication, learning, and collaboration shape inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge production. However, it is applicable to a wide range of audiences.

Team leadership and team effectiveness

Lab dynamics: Management and leadership skills for scientists. Cohen, C. M., & Cohen, S. L. (2018). Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press

- ➔ Much more geared toward team leaders, principal investigators (PIs) and other leadership or administrative personnel, such as directors. It is a practical guide on how to build productive laboratory cultures although this applies outside of stereotypical lab settings as well. This is also a great read for PIs applying for large funding for new labs or cross-institute programs.

Leading teams: Setting the stage for great performances. Hackman, J. R. (2002). Harvard Business Press.

- ➔ One of the more “classical” SciTS related books for leaders (i.e., PIs, managers, etc) and scholars explaining how team design, context, and coaching create conditions for sustained team performance and productivity. Even though this is targeted at leaders, the practical and tacit knowledge provided is also of value to graduate students and postdoctoral associates (especially for those starting to apply for larger funding and stepping into greater leadership roles in their careers).

Teams that work: The seven drivers of team effectiveness. Tannenbaum, S. I., & Salas, E. (2020). Oxford University Press.

- ➔ An evidence-based practitioner-academic guide for managers and researchers explaining what distinguishes effective teams especially in terms of team design, capabilities, norms, cohesion, and learning. Especially for those new to team science, the insights from Dr. Salas are especially valuable given his time in the field. We recommend seeing his other work [here](#).

Creating effective teams: A guide for members and leaders. Wheelan, S. A., Akerlund, M., & Jacobsson, C. (2024). SAGE.

- ➔ Compared to the other guides in this section, this book is more accessible to students in general, although it is also of value to leaders, scientists and practitioners focused on team development, member responsibilities/roles, and leader behaviors that improve team functioning. Unlike books coming from an academic approach, the insights offered here

Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado **Boulder**

come from consultants, so this is based on facilitator experiences. It could be used in a graduate course or a upper level undergraduate course on leadership since it focuses on demystifying the “stages” of teaming.

Group dynamics for teams. Levi, D., & Askay, D. A. (2025). SAGE.

- ➔ Continuing with books more geared for students, this textbook for students covers the breadth of group dynamics concepts and goals, including the importance of communication, diversity, decision making, managing conflict, teamwork, and organizational context. This is also a nice entry point for postdoctoral associates who are new to team science and group dynamics in general and want to do some self-study.

Team cognition, multiteam systems, and applied teamwork

Theories of team cognition: Cross-disciplinary perspectives. Salas, E., Fiore, S. M., & Letsky, M. P. (Eds.). (2012). Routledge.

- ➔ This book focuses on team cognition and provides a psychological perspective. While team cognition and team science are separate fields they overlap with each other extensively. This book bridges cognitive science and teamwork research. It is particularly valuable for scholars studying how scientific teams think. The book provides insights on organizational behavior, teaming, communication, and social psychology.

The Wiley Blackwell handbook of the psychology of team working and collaborative processes. Salas, E., Rico, R., & Passmore, J. (Eds.). (2017). Wiley Blackwell.

- ➔ A handbook for organizational psychologists and advanced practitioners reviewing contemporary evidence on design, diversity, leadership, trust, measurement, and collaboration in teams.

Foundations and theoretical perspectives of distributed team cognition. McNeese, M., Salas, E., & Endsley, M. R. (Eds.). (2021). CRC Press.

- ➔ For advanced researchers examining how team cognition is distributed across people, technologies, tasks, and time in contemporary collaborative systems.

Multiteam systems: An organization form for dynamic and complex environments. Zaccaro, S. J., Marks, M. A., & DeChurch, L. A. (Eds.). (2012). Routledge.

- ➔ For advanced researchers and leaders studying coordination among multiple interdependent teams operating in complex, dynamic, and/or distributed settings. This is a great overview of multiteam systems in general, and provides additional insights on MTS applicable to how doing science is organized today (i.e., increasingly complex problems needing increasingly complex teams).

Improving patient safety through teamwork and team training. Salas, E., & Frush, K. (Eds.). (2013). Oxford University Press.

Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences
University of Colorado **Boulder**

- ➔ Provides a more health and biomedical perspective on the benefits of teamwork for healthcare teams (and for clinical team science). This evidence-based book is especially valuable to healthcare leaders, educators, and researchers on teamwork principles, training design, and performance improvement in high-stakes environments, such as in healthcare.

When teams work best: 6,000 team members and leaders tell what it takes to succeed.

LaFasto, F. M. J., & Larson, C. E. (2001). SAGE.

- ➔ This is one of the seminal works on team effectiveness. This is more of a practitioner-oriented synthesis for leaders and facilitators drawing on large-scale team interviews to identify the recurring components of successful teamwork. This is an update to LaFasto and Larson's work from 1989.

Teamwork: What must go right/what can go wrong. Larson, C. E., & LaFasto, F. M. J. (1989). SAGE.

- ➔ A classic within team effectiveness. This book is for both leaders and students that distills core conditions, common failures, and practical diagnostics for group performance.

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